

Building a Reservoir of Data for Dam Design – Comprehensive Geophysical and Geological Site Characterization for Efficiency and Cost Savings Across the Project Lifespan

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ABSTRACT

Complex geology poses challenges to construction of major infrastructure. Here we present perspectives from a project to develop a 96,000 acre-foot reservoir with four dams totaling 10,000 linear feet in Colorado’s Rocky Mountains. Proactively building a comprehensive, 3D geologic/geotechnical model has been key to overcoming geologic complexity, and site-wide geophysical imaging has been key to building that model economically and quickly. Gravity surveys efficiently provided the basis for the model and guided dam layout. More involved seismic and borehole investigations then focused on dam alignments and specific areas of interest. The 3D modeling reduced project cost by allowing us to avoid problematic units, take advantage of favorable structures (e.g., bedrock highs), estimate foundation excavation depths, and identify onsite quarry material. We conclude that comprehensive 3D geotechnical models can optimize planning and design, and that geophysics provides a strong base for these models, even in the most challenging geologic settings.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of the local geology is critical to planning and design of major infrastructure such as reservoirs and the associated dams. For example, there may be geologic units that are problematic for geotechnical or hydrogeologic reasons; by contrast, buried bedrock highs, strong caprock, or low-permeability seals can provide favorable conditions. Physical properties of the foundation rock control how much excavation, grouting, or other foundation treatment is necessary, with profound impacts on construction costs. Identifying borrow areas or quarries onsite reduces or eliminates the expense of transporting construction material. For these and other reasons, a 3D geologic and geotechnical model of the site can be indispensable in cost estimation, avoiding project delays, and optimizing design.

Borehole investigations are essential to determining physical properties of subsurface units. Metrics such as standard penetration test (SPT) blowcounts or rock quality designation (RQD) constrain in-situ strength. Packer, injection, and pumping tests are used to estimate bulk hydrologic parameters. Shear and compressive strength, chemistry, density, and many other physical properties of cores and other samples can be tested in the laboratory. Where local geology is uniform, building a 3D model for planning and design is trivial: A handful of boreholes provide the necessary information on geotechnical properties and their range of variations. The approach need not be much different for sites where two or a few geologic units are present: As long as geologic maps are available, one or more holes can target each rock/soil type for sampling and testing, and the associated parameter values can be assigned to the units.

In situations of extreme geologic complexity, however, the time and cost required to core, sample, and test enough boreholes may be prohibitive. Moreover, borehole observations only provide information at discrete locations, so interpolations incompletely resolve lateral changes, and the model is entirely blind to anomalies between borings. Narrow, critical features such as buried channels, dikes, faults, or karst voids will be missed entirely unless a borehole happens to intercept them.

Here, we discuss the process of constructing a 3D geotechnical model for a planned 96,000 acre-foot (ft) reservoir site in the central Colorado Rockies requiring four separate dams totaling 10,000 linear ft (**Figures 1–2**). Challenges at the site include evaporite karst, dozens of cross-cutting faults, and incompletely mapped heterogeneous volcanic stratigraphy, while rich cultural resources including more than 200 ceremonial sites, graves, and other avoidance zones preclude intrusive exploration in much of the area. A multi-year phased approach has used geophysical imaging to integrate the normally disparate geologic site characterization, reservoir layout, dam and foundation design, and construction planning. First, efficient and non-invasive microgravity (microGal-precision relative gravity) surveys provided a coarse yet comprehensive site-wide model within days, delineating the most problematic geology. With this data, the reservoir layout was redrafted to avoid these features and to take advantage of a structural basin lined by locally sourced volcanic flows. Higher-resolution microgravity along the draft alignments then identified subsurface bedrock ridges that further guided alignment of the dams, and bedrock topography estimates were incorporated into foundation designs to optimize stability and minimize excavation. Targeted 2D/3D seismic imaging provided additional detail of areas of interest along the alignments, such as buried channels and fault zones, provided estimates of geotechnical moduli, and allowed much more efficient siting of subsequent invasive investigations. With more than 150 boreholes—averaging 45 meters (m) depth (150 ft)—now completed, empirical geotechnical data and geologic “ground truth” ultimately guided dam and construction design, from siting to seismic design and from on-site sourcing of quarries and fill material to hydrogeologic modeling.

Figure 1: Project location

The investment in robust site characterization that unifies geology, geophysics, and geotechnical and civil engineering lays the foundation for integrated planning, design, and construction, providing efficiency and cost savings throughout the project lifespan. Based on our experiences through this project, we offer the following general workflow:

- **Site reconnaissance, feasibility:** Coarse, site-wide gravity survey supplemented by existing or additional geologic mapping.
- **Reservoir layout, dam alignment:** Higher-resolution gravity of the planned reservoir footprint, 2D/3D seismic in key or questionable sections of foundation(s), borehole confirmation of foundation suitability.
- **Engineering design:** Seismic constraints on foundation Vs30, gravity/seismic identification of borrow and quarry areas, boreholes for in-situ geotechnical parameters, 3D hydrogeologic modeling.
- **Construction design and costing:** Gravity/seismic predictions of foundation excavation depths and grout extents, seismic estimates of rippability.

The Wild Horse Reservoir Project

The City of Aurora Water Department is planning development of the Wild Horse Reservoir in South Park, Colorado, ~8 kilometers (km; ~5 miles) south of Hartsel (**Figure 1**). The reservoir occupies a broad, sparsely vegetated valley with low hills that create up to 30 m (100 ft) of relief. The valley is mostly internally drained, with gentle inward slopes on its eastern, southern, and western sides. The ~120 m-tall (~400-ft) granitic

Wild Horse Hills basement uplift impounds the basin to the north; a narrow canyon winds northward through this crystalline block to a wind gap. Elevations range from 2725 m (8940 ft) within that canyon to 2876 m at the Wild Horse Hills highpoint; the broad valley sits near 2740 m (9000 ft).

The project plan includes construction of dams at four sites (**Figures 1–2**) that supplement the natural topography to provide a normal water surface elevation at 2383 m (9074 ft) and a crest at 2385 m (9085 ft). The Main Dam will rise more than 60 m (200 ft) across the narrow canyon cut through the Wild Horse Hills, spanning some 300 m (~1000 ft). Southeast of there, the East Dams will

comprise a pair of ~20-m-tall (~60-ft) saddle dams totaling some 600 m (~2000 ft) in length. Finally, the southern and western sides of the reservoir will be impounded by the left and right arms of the West Dam, respectively. The ~900-m-long (2900-ft) left arm descends the western slope of a cauldron-shaped volcanic cone (**Figure 2**) then climbs a ridge of volcanic rock to the West Dam’s “elbow”. The right arm trends 1300 m (~4200 ft) north-northwest along this ridge, which is cut near the middle by the ~15 m (~50 ft) deep, 150 m (~500 ft) wide Agate Creek “paleovalley”.

Tetra Tech began ongoing work in July 2020. At that time, the proposed reservoir occupied a ~10 km x 4 km footprint (purple outline in **Figure 3**). However, feasibility studies had identified dozens of closed surface depressions near the southern end of this alignment (RJH, 2020) attributed to dissolution of Paleozoic evaporites (Tetra Tech 2021a) that impugned the viability of a reservoir at the site. To differentiate it from the alignment that is currently being considered (blue outline in **Figure 3**), this configuration will be referred to as the previous dam alignment in this manuscript. Over the past five years, project objectives have included:

- Identify the largest reservoir (up to 96,000 acre-feet) that can be safely developed at the site.
- Identify the locations and configurations of the necessary dams.
- Estimate seepage losses.
- Collect data on subsurface material properties, foundation conditions, and permeability of subsurface units and features to support Feasibility Design of the dams and reservoir.
- Collect subsurface data to characterize excavation limits and foundation treatment requirements for 30% Design of the dams and reservoir.
- Identify onsite fine-grained borrow material and rock quarry locations

GEOLOGY

The tectonic history of the site (**Appendix A**) includes ~1.6 and ~1.4 Ga accretion events, ~1.0 Ga plutonism, the Paleozoic Ancestral Rockies intraplate orogeny, the Late Cretaceous/Early Tertiary intraplate Laramide orogeny, and Cenozoic extension. The Antero Reservoir NE Quad (Barkmann et al., 2018) provides the base for field investigation. Nevertheless, the subsurface geologic structure of the site was not well defined because it is concealed by up to hundreds of feet (100+ m) of volcanic deposits. Previous boreholes did not extend deep enough to measure volcanic deposit thicknesses or penetrate geologic units below. Site-specific mapping, borehole and geophysical data, and more precise fault and fold delineation build on this base map (**Figure 3**).

Tectonic Features

Laramide uplift on the Agate Creek Anticline and of the Wild Horse Hills along the 31 Mile-Buffer Buffalo Gulch fault (31MBGF) created a basin similar to the present reservoir footprint. The site is also rife with sub-orthogonal tear faults that trend northeast from the Agate Creek fault, however (Barkmann et al., 2018). The most prominent

Figure 2: Reservoir layout and primary physiographic features

Figure 3: Geologic map with borehole locations and geophysical surveys from prior studies. Abbreviations of units discussed below – Xg/Xgp (granite/porphyritic granite), Xmi (mafic dikes), Peem/s/c (Echo Park), P_lwm (Wall Mtn Tuff), Peam (Andesite), P_lba (Breccia), P_ltc (Tallahassee Creek), P_la (Antero)

of these is the Poyner Ranch fault (PRF). Lateral motion on these faults compartmentalized deformation by allowing different amounts of shortening between adjacent blocks, with secondary northwest-side-up offsets (observed in boreholes TT-15-20 vs. TT-16-20, and TT-21-21 vs. TT-22-21) (**Figure 3**). Combined motion on compartment faults and the Agate Creek Anticline has exposed a basement block at the northwest edge of the reservoir, termed the “NW massif”.

Local Volcanism

Volcanic bombs were encountered within the 34.3 Ma Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch (Breccia) in numerous boreholes along the West Dam alignment, in TT-16-20 near the East Dam, and in abundance in a test trench across the PRF. Maximum bomb diameters decreased to the northwest from 2 meters (5–7 feet) in that trench to 0.7 m (2 ft) in TT-16-20 and 0.5 m (1.7 ft) in TT-12-20 near the West Dam right abutment (**Figure 4**). Ballistics trajectories (calculated following Mastin, 2001) triangulate the source to an obvious, cauldron-shaped hill at the southeast corner of the proposed reservoir (**Figure 4**). Blocky hills composed of Breccia trend northwest from this cone into the proposed reservoir, and the northwest rim of the cone itself is absent (**Figures 2–4**). For these and additional reasons, Tetra Tech (2021) concluded that the cauldron-shaped hill is the remnant of a small volcano, and failure of its northwestern flank at 34.3 Ma poured into a basin—the Agate Creek Syncline—between the Agate Creek Anticline and the 31MBGF/Hartsel Uplift. The basin was likely already a volcanic hellscape partially filled with more distally sourced Wall Mountain Tuff (Tuff) and Middle Andesite Series (Andesite). To the extent that the chaotic Breccia deposits are stratified, they dip northwest off the cone into the reservoir. By contrast, on the west side of the basin Breccia flows and ejecta lapped onto a pre-existing topographic ridge atop the Agate Creek Anticline and therefore dip back eastward into the reservoir (see subsurface imaging discussed below).

Stratigraphy - The Old, the Young, and the Crummy

More than a dozen rock types are present within the study area, ranging in age from Paleoproterozoic to Recent (**Figure 3; Appendix B**). Constraining the distributions and geotechnical properties of each unit are primary goals of the project.

Paleoproterozoic granites exposed in the Wild Horse Hills and NW massif underlie the entire area. The most competent rocks onsite, these are suitable for dam foundations and may provide quarry material for dam construction.

The abundant volcanic rocks provide reasonable foundation material—with varying amounts of grouting anticipated—but do not yield sufficiently large boulders for dam construction. Hundreds of ft (50–100+ m) of Breccia and Andesite are present west of 31MBGF, likely with even thicker deposits of Tuff below. The Tuff and underlying Lower Volcaniclastic Unit only outcrop east of 31MBGF.

Four sedimentary rock units present at the site are problematic. The poorly lithified, latest Eocene Tallahassee Creek and Antero sedimentary formations are widespread south and west of the proposed reservoir. Closed depressions within the Antero impugned the feasibility of the previous configuration. Prior work (RJH, 2020) suggested that these depressions were the result of dissolution of evaporites in the Paleozoic Minturn Formation. Tetra Tech (2021a) reprocessed RJH seismic line 4, at the southern end of that reservoir configuration (see **Figure 3**): A stack of east-vergent backthrusts in the hangingwall (i.e., east side) of the Agate Creek fault appear to have transported the Minturn to within ~100 ft (~30 m) of the surface (**Figure 5**). Moreover, multiple low-velocity pockets that may be water-filled voids were imaged near the top of the presumed Minturn evaporite facies. These three units appear unsuitable for dam foundations, likely requiring excavation or extensive grouting. Dam centerlines in the current alignment were drafted to entirely avoid these units, except for a ~110-m (~365-ft) stretch of the West Dam near the right abutment that crosses a pocket of Tallahassee Creek.

Figure 4: Triangulating the source of the Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch

Figure 5

Figure 5: Blind basement uplift and shallow Minturn formation (Pme) beneath the previous reservoir alignment. Reprocessed RJH seismic line 4 (see location on Figure 3).

Characterization of the final unfavorable unit, the Eocene Echo Park conglomerate, is ongoing. Only encountered in the right half of the East Dam, where it sits unconformably atop basement, the Echo Park displayed high permeability in Packer tests near the right abutment. Subsequent pumping tests were equivocal, however. Work is ongoing to characterize the hydrogeologic behavior of this unit, to determine its thickness with deeper boreholes near the East Dam right abutment, and to define its lateral extents in that area with geophysics.

GEOPHYSICAL INVESTIGATIONS - GRAVITY

We have collected 3419 readings at 3027 unique locations (**Figure 6**). Data are reduced to the Complete Bouguer Anomaly (CBA); a polynomial regional trend is fit to and subtracted from CBA to isolate the gravity signals due to density variations beneath the site, termed the “residual gravity anomaly” or “residual”. Details of data acquisition and processing are given in **Appendix C**.

The residual gravity anomaly is the basis for interpretations and for four avenues of further analysis. High-pass/band-pass filtering emphasizes signals from specific depth ranges. First, second, and third horizontal derivatives illuminate structural trends and the faults that truncate them. Analytical models estimate depths to bedrock or thickness of specific units. Inversions generate 3D subsurface models.

Residual Gravity Anomaly

The residual gravity anomaly (**Figure 6**) illuminates the main features of the site: two crystalline uplifts, two blind basement uplifts, the major Antero Syncline, the composite Agate Creek Syncline, and a caldera-like volcanic cone.

- Crystalline rock produces distinctive gravity highs in the Wild Horse Hills and NW massif.
- The blind Agate Creek Anticline creates a moderate high-gravity anomaly that extends southward from the NW crystalline uplift and underlies the right arm of the West Dam.
- South of the reservoir, a prominent gravity high south of the Poyner Ranch fault is interpreted as a mostly blind basement uplift.
- The Antero Syncline creates a large negative gravity anomaly along the western edge of the study area.
- The Agate Creek Syncline exhibits a lower-amplitude negative anomaly bounded on the east by the Wild Horse Hills and on the west by the NW massif and Agate Creek Anticline. This Agate Creek Syncline anomaly separates into three parts: a basin north of the Main Dam canyon and west of graben formed by the 31MBGF and an antithetic fault, a 31MBGF footwall

Figure 6: Residual gravity anomaly across the greater study area. Negative anomalies (blue) delineate basins. Positive anomalies (red) correspond with basement uplifts. (A) Shown with locations of gravity measurements (n=3419). (B) Major features are labeled.

half graben between the Main Dam canyon and the Poyner Ranch Faults, and the cauldron-shaped hill thought to be a local volcanic center. Notably, a ~500-m-wide (~1500 ft) zone of subdued gravity anomaly separates the full graben north of the Main Dam canyon from the half graben footwall basin. This break may be a subtle structural high along a NE-trending compartment fault.

- East of the 31MBGF and just north of the Poyner Ranch fault, the mafic dike complex manifests as a local gravity maximum, exceeding the high gravity in the adjacent granitic Wild Horse Hills; this feature is most obvious in the high-pass filtered anomaly (e.g., **Figure 7**).

First, second, and third horizontal derivatives of the residual gravity anomaly constrain the locations of geologic contacts, faults, and folds. These models and their derivations are presented in **Appendix C**.

High-pass/Low-pass Filtering: Isolating Signals from Pertinent Depths

Deeper density anomalies generate broader gravity signals. Removing long-wavelength patterns emphasizes shallow sources, a process termed high-pass filtering. We have developed spatial-domain algorithms to accentuate signals from specific depths (**Appendix C**). For instance, the 200-meter filter applied in **Figure 7** focuses on contrasts within the upper ~200 meters (~650 feet).

- The most positive high-pass anomalies delineate the NW massif and mafic dikes at the East Dam.
- In the Agate Creek Syncline, high-pass filtering clarifies the break between the full-graben basin north of the Main Dam canyon and the half-graben to the south.
- A low-gravity trend northwest from the cauldron-shaped cone is interpreted as the collapsed northwest flank of the small volcano that poured into a pre-existing synclinal basin between 31MBGF and Agate Creek Anticline.

Figure 7: High-pass filtered (200 m) gravity anomaly: (Left) The greater study area, same region as Figure 6; opaque. (Right) Same model, semi-transparent, overlain on geology, and zoomed in on the proposed reservoir footprint.

Gravimetric Tomography

Seismic tomography is a mainstay of geophysical imaging. We have developed proprietary 3D gravimetric tomography to provide comprehensive imaging of the subsurface across a ~5x7 km (~3x5 mile) area centered on the site (**Figure 8**). Comparisons between the derived 3D density structure and 2D/3D seismic tomography are favorable, although the horizontal resolution of the gravimetry is limited to approximately the local station spacing.

From a project perspective, however, the costs associated with the 5x7 km gravity model are similar to costs for two ~150x150 m (500x500 ft) seismic surveys.

Figure 8: Gravimetric tomography cross section. Location shown at right. (Top) Relative density variations. This view accentuates geologic structures. (Bottom) Same location, showing modeled absolute densities to aid in interpreting geologic units.

GEOPHYSICAL INVESTIGATIONS - SEISMIC

In addition to reprocessing prior seismic data (e.g., **Figure 5**), new seismic surveys have been conducted in more than a dozen areas across the site:

- 2D profiles
 - across the Main Dam right abutment (outlet tunnel alignment)
 - along the East Dam centerline,
 - along the East Dam spillway,
 - across the East Dam along County Road 53,
 - across the central part of West Dam left arm
 - across the northern West Dam right arm in three locations
 - along two stretches of the northern West Dam right arm
 - southwest of the West Dam elbow
- 3D volumes
 - Main Dam footprint
 - 31MBGF between the Main Dam canyon and East Dam
 - Agate Creek Paleovalley (central West Dam right arm)
 - Northern West Dam right arm, exploiting the SPT hammer as a source at depth

These data have been processed and inverted using standard methods such as multi-channel analysis of shear waves and refraction tomography, advanced methods such as 3D finite-frequency tomography and full-waveform inversion, and a unique approach that exploits signals from borehole work. Specifically, the latter technique (Mirzanejad et al., 2020) attaches a seismic trigger to the hammer used for SPT testing and lays out a grid of sensors on the surface; the hammer blows then serve as a source at depth, providing source-to-sensor paths than necessarily travel through the subsurface material of interest rather than relying on turning rays and refractions.

Seismic investigations can provide direct inputs for engineering design. Seismic design ground motions depend on Vs30, the time-averaged shear-wave velocity (Vs) in the upper 30 m (100 ft): Higher shaking is anticipated with decreasing Vs30 (i.e., softer foundation rock), resulting in higher construction costs to build stronger dams capable of withstanding those motions. Therefore, it can be economically advantageous to invest in excavating shallow low-velocity material to increase Vs30 in the dam foundation. We have derived one-dimensional Vs profiles for each dam alignment (e.g., **Figure 9A**) and calculated curves of Vs30 vs. pre-construction excavation depth (**Figure 9B**), allowing the tradeoff to be optimized between the cost of excavation and the stiffer foundation that would result.

Seismic models can also aid in the estimation of pre-construction costs. Foundation preparation involves excavation of weak material, for example removal of soil and saprolite with SPT blowcounts $N < 50$ (i.e., depth to refusal). This excavation is a substantial component of construction costs. N-values vs. depth were tabulated for each of the boreholes, but these observations provide no constraint on the depth of excavation anticipated at locations between boreholes, leaving large uncertainties in future expenses. By contrast, seismic models generated for each of the dams avail continuous estimates of physical properties. Therefore, the velocity where $N=50$ in one borehole serves as a proxy for refusal in nearby areas without direct constraints. For instance, we have found that refusal consistently coincides with ~ 5000 ft/sec P-velocity beneath both arms of the West Dam and the East Dam. The depth to this velocity contour thus provides a 2D estimate of the thickness of material that will be excavated for foundation preparation (Figure 10), and this anticipated excavation volume factors prominently in construction cost estimates.

Figure 9: (A) 1D velocity profile beneath the East Dam. (B) Vs30 as a function of excavation depth.

Figure 10: Seismically estimated depth to SPT N=50 along the West Dam right arm. Location shown in top left inset. This model provides a preliminary 2D estimate of the depth of excavation that will be required during foundation preparation. Orange stars: Boreholes. Brown & cyan: Proposed dam footprint.

DATA SYNTHESIS: 3D GEOLOGIC AND GEOTECHNICAL MODEL

Alone, none of the subsurface exploration techniques used in this project—boreholes, seismic, and gravity—is sufficient. Boreholes avail the in-situ geotechnical parameters needed for engineering design, but only at one specific location. Seismic surveys can be conducted without damaging resources and provide estimates of material properties such as rippability; however, those estimates are imprecise and only applicable within the survey footprint. Gravity is only sensitive to the density of materials, yet modeling provides constraints on 3D structure, and gravity data can be collected more quickly and at a fraction of the cost for similar resolution from seismic or boreholes.

Synthesizing all of these sources of information allows for efficient progress along the project's critical path (**Figure 11**). The seismic model shown in **Figure 10** provides more detailed estimates of the depth of high-quality foundation rock than possible from the four boreholes within the bounds of the seismic survey, yet the boreholes are necessary to determine the local velocity of that stiff material. Moreover, the seismic estimates (calibrated to the local boreholes) can then be rapidly expanded using gravity, which can cover 10-40 times more area than 3D seismic for the same time and monetary cost.

Figure 11: Multi-method delineation of shallow high-quality foundation rock along the West Dam right arm. (A) The seismic model shown in Figure 10. (B) High-pass filtered gravity in the same area as panel A. Black box shows the area resolved by the seismic survey in panel A. Negative anomalies delineate low-quality Tallahassee Creek conglomerate on the flanks of the Agate Creek anticline. Positive anomalies indicate shallow competent rock along the anticline. Using this information, the West Dam was configured to take advantage of the shallow bedrock ridge, improving foundation quality, reducing anticipated leakage, and decreasing projected construction costs.

Finally, the subsurface geologic and geotechnical data collected at the site have been synthesized in a 3D Leapfrog model. This model is designed for hydrogeologic simulations, but it can easily be queried for actionable information at any depth and location, including SPT N values, geologic units, permeability, or other parameters or to provide a continuous surface, such as for excavation planning. Cross sections beneath each of the dam alignments (**Figures 12–15**) provide the most comprehensive and applicable summary of findings. In each figure, borehole data (RQD, geologic unit, water table, SPT N counts, and discrete permeability) are shown, while the geophysical data are used to constrain the lateral extents of units and to constrain the geologic/geotechnical/hydrologic model away from the boreholes, which are focused on the dam alignments.

Figure 12: Main Dam centerline cross-section through 3D geotechnical model.

Figure 13: East Dam centerline cross-section through 3D geotechnical model.

Figure 14: West Dam left arm centerline cross-section through 3D geotechnical model.

Figure 15: West Dam right arm centerline cross-section through 3D geotechnical model

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Appendix A: Tectonic History

The Phanerozoic history of central Colorado comprises three principal tectonic events: the Pennsylvanian–Permian Ancestral Rockies orogeny, the Laramide orogeny, Oligocene–ongoing period of extension discussed in the next section. Nearly all structures and geologic units preserved in South Park represent one of these three events, and often some combination thereof.

There may be additional influences from Precambrian events, including the ~1.6–1.4 Ga accretion of the Yavapai and Mazatzal terranes that comprise much of modern Colorado and northern New Mexico to the Archean core of North America (the Wyoming Craton), accretion of island arcs and other small terranes, and extensive ~1.0 Ga plutonism roughly coeval with the assembly of Rodinia and associated intraplate deformation (e.g., the Midcontinent Rift, Oklahoma Aulacogen, and Grenville Orogeny) (e.g., Whitmeyer & Karlstrom, 2007).

Paleozoic Ancestral Rockies Orogeny

The Ancestral Rockies orogeny was part of a nearly continent-wide series of Paleozoic contractile deformation events associated with the collision of Laurentia (proto-North America) with island arcs and eventually Eurasia during the closure of the Iapetus Ocean and assembly of Pangaea. Beginning in the eastern United States with three (or more) discrete Appalachian orogenic events, deformation continued southward along the Ouachita and then Marathon trends in Arkansas, Oklahoma, and Texas before turning back northward to impact what is now Colorado.

Two sub-parallel NNW-trending basement-cored uplifts grew in the area that now makes up the central Rockies. Frontrangia (roughly coincident with the modern Front Range) and Uncompahgre (roughly coincident with the Uncompahgre Uplift) were separated by the structural and thrust-loaded Central Colorado Trough. The Trough was internally drained throughout most of its history and therefore collected the synorogenic sediments of the Maroon Formation (correlative with the Fountain Formation) and the evaporites and carbonates of the Minturn Formation. North of Hartsel, the boundary between Frontrangia and the Colorado Trough was roughly coincident with the modern structural, topographic, and physiographic eastern edge of South Park. Near Hartsel, the Frontrangia-Colorado Trough boundary stepped rightward into what is now the center of South Park along an ENE-trending tear fault termed the Hartsel Fault Zone (HFZ). Now largely obscured by younger rocks and pervasively overprinted by Laramide and more recent deformation, the displaced Paleozoic boundary now lies near the center of southern South Park, trending roughly southward from Hartsel very near the site. Barkmann et al. (2018) posit that the Hartsel Uplift may have been the boundary between Frontrangia to the east and the Trough to the west. Motion on the block-bounding faults would therefore have controlled the shoreline location and ultimately deposition of evaporitic facies in the Minturn Formation.

Exposed Precambrian crystalline rocks—including those in the Main Dam canyon—are anomalous relative to the rest of central South Park, which is a structural syncline, typically cored by the relatively youngest rocks. This basement high, the Hartsel Uplift or Wild Horse Hills, appears to terminate at the HFZ. The HFZ bends southward (equivalent to taking a left step) near Hartsel, which would have been a restraining bend in the Paleozoic dextral shear system. Numerous anastomosing fault strands south of Hartsel resemble the positive flower structure expected in such a geometry and suggest that the Hartsel Uplift originated or was rejuvenated as a transpressive feature during Ancestral Rockies time.

Mesozoic Quiescence and the Laramide Orogeny

Following the Ancestral Rockies deformation recorded by the Maroon and Minturn formations, Mesozoic units document widespread quiescence and erosion. A series of regressions and transgressions of the Western Interior Seaway during the Cretaceous is represented by the Entrada Sandstone, Morrison Formation (mainly muds and minor evaporites), Dakota Sandstone, Niobrara Limestone and associated shales, Pierre Shale, and Fox Hills/Laramie Sandstones. These units are absent in the project site: Either the area remained elevated into the Cretaceous so these units were never deposited, or faulting, uplift, and erosion during and after the Laramide Orogeny stripped them entirely.

The Laramide Orogeny renewed deformation in the late Cretaceous and into the early Tertiary. Resulting from the subduction of the Farallon plate beneath western North America, Laramide thick-skinned thrusting occurred more than 1,000 km from the plate boundary – a commonality with the intraplate Ancestral Rockies. Although the exact mechanics of this intraplate orogeny are debated (c.f., Bird, 1988; Jones et al., 2011), most theories invoke basal shear stress generated by shallow to flat subduction of the Farallon slab. Approximately E–W shortening created the modern thrust faults that bound South Park and likely reactivated the HFZ, augmenting

the Hartsel Uplift (e.g., Barkmann et al., 2018). Reverse motion on both west-vergent thrust faults and east-vergent backthrusts accommodated shortening, while ENE-trending tear faults compartmentalized deformation in discrete structural blocks, allowing different amounts of shortening from one block to the next.

Tertiary Deformation and Volcanism

As the Mendocino Fracture Zone was subducted beneath southern California during the Oligocene (Atwater, 1970), increasing portions of the western North American margin shifted from subduction to dominantly dextral motion (McQuarrie and Wernicke, 2005). This change relaxed the E-W compressional traction applied to the North America plate and allowed for asthenospheric upwelling in the slab window between the subducting Farallon slab and the base of the North American lithosphere. This influx of asthenospheric material allowed the subducting slab to decouple from the overriding lithosphere, steepening (or “rolling back”) and descending into the mantle (Humphreys, 1995). Decoupling of the negatively buoyant slab triggered isostatic rebound of overlying North America. This uplift increased lithospheric gravitational potential energy (e.g., Levandowski et al., 2014), which combined with waning compression from the western margin (e.g., Flesch et al., 2000) to cause a rapid shift from contraction to extension across western North America (Jones et al., 1996). Simultaneously, slab rollback supplied fresh, warm asthenosphere to the lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary, quickly heating the newly hydrated North American lithosphere and triggering widespread melt generation (Humphreys et al., 2003), which manifests in southern South Park in abundant Tertiary volcanic and volcanoclastic units including as the prominent Thirtynine-Mile suite. Similar units are present across the western United States. Varying interactions between mafic, hydrous melts and continental crust resulted in a wide range of igneous compositions including prototypical “crystal mush” plutonism and sporadic, bimodal extrusives (e.g., Farmer et al., 2008).

Appendix B: Stratigraphy and Geologic Characterization

Surficial and other Quaternary Units (Qxs)

The highly weathered saprolite Surficial units are mapped as Quaternary alluvium with smaller colluvial deposits locally present (Barkmann et al., 2018). The soils encountered in the test trench, test pits, and borings were mainly classified as sand, sand to sandy clays, and sandy silts. Saprolite, which is previously subaerially exposed, weathered-in-place rock that behaves like soil in the SPT samples, is encountered in most locations and comprises clay and silt derived from weathered ash and less-weathered, small, resistant volcanic sand to gravel sized clasts.

Outside of the reservoir footprint, recent gypsum deposits along the present-day Agate Creek north and west of the project area (**Figure 2**) indicate a local gypsum dissolution and mineral reprecipitation in the nearby playas (Barkmann et al., 2018). No evidence or outcrops of gypsiferous strata are found along or east of the Agate Creek Anticline or within the reservoir footprint.

SPT sampling in the borings was completed from the surface to depths between 14 feet to 76 feet. This thickness includes the completely weathered bedrock (saprolite) which was too soft for HQ coring.

Antero Formation (PEa)

The crumbly Antero Formation is mapped south and west of the proposed reservoir footprint. Earlier dam alignments had included areas underlain by this poorly consolidated, reworked ash and pumice conglomerate. The revised dam alignments proposed in this work avoid the problematic unit, and it appears to be entirely absent within the current footprint. This unit was only encountered as highly weathered saprolite in TT-01-20 and TT-02-20, each within ~300 feet of the PRF and south of the reservoir.

Tallahassee Creek Conglomerate (PEtc)

Tallahassee Creek Conglomerate was encountered in boreholes on the upstream and downstream toes of the West Dam and in TT-31 along the centerline but is mainly restricted to areas west of the Agate Creek Anticline and the flanks of the NW basement uplift. Highly weathered Tallahassee Creek Conglomerate consisted of yellowish brown, gray, and grayish brown sandy siltstone that was medium stiff to very stiff. The siltstone was friable and thinly bedded with poorly graded fine to medium grained sand. The samples contained limestone, sandstone, shale, and conglomerate lithics up to 0.2 feet in diameter. The siltstone broke apart when water was applied. A highly weathered sandstone interval was encountered from 20 feet bgs to 25 feet bgs. The sandstone was bedded and cross bedded and consisted of predominately fine-grained quartz sand. The sand was oxidized to an orange-red color.

The Tallahassee Creek Conglomerate core samples generally consisted of fresh, weak to medium strong, olive gray interbedded sandy shale; tuffaceous, silty sandstone; and tuffaceous, matrix-supported conglomerate. The shale was laminated with 1 mm to 2 mm thick beds to massive. The shale also had plant matter and occasional lithics up to 2 mm long. The sandstone was moderately sorted with fine to medium grained sand composed generally of approximately 65% quartz, 10% plagioclase, 20% ash, 15% biotite. The sandstone contained plant matter and limestone lithics up to 0.1 feet in diameter. The conglomerate was massive and polymictic with varicolored clasts. Clasts were composed of petrified wood, shale, rhyolite, and sandstone.

Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch (PEbb)

The Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch was encountered in most of the borings along the West Dam alignment. Highly weathered saprolite Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch (saprolite) consisted of weak red, pale red, and grayish red sandy silt and sandy clay with gravel clasts that were medium stiff to hard. A medium dense to very dense silty sand was also encountered. The saprolite Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch was brownish yellow where oxidized. The samples had occasional intervals with zeolite-like and calcite minerals in the matrix.

Core samples of the Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch unit were generally highly weathered to fresh, with decreasing degrees of weathering in depth. The Volcanic Breccia of Buffalo Gulch core was extremely weak to strong, and pale red, brownish gray, and grayish red. The rock was polymictic w/varicolored subrounded to subangular clasts from granules to greater than 0.5-ft diameter in fine-grained matrix. The clasts were generally composed of rhyolite, andesite, sandstone, claystone, tuff, and vitrophyre. The rock was matrix-supported. Clasts were often vuggy with the vugs partially filled with calcite, chlorite, and silica.

Middle Andesite Series (P_{Eam})

The Middle Andesite Series was encountered in multiple boreholes in the West Dam area at various depths ranging from ground surface in borehole TT-37-21 to a maximum of 192 ft bgs in borehole TT-01-20. Multiple factors from the geologic history of the area contribute to the varying depths at which rocks from the Middle Andesite Series were encountered. Andesitic rocks are formed from blocky lava flows which cover the existing topography with thicker deposits in low areas and thin covers, if any, over relatively higher areas, depending on flow volume and terrain conditions. In addition, blocky andesitic lava flows typically produce rough, irregular surfaces, which—when covered with deposits from later episodes of explosive volcanic activity, such as the overlying Volcanic Breccia of the Buffalo Gulch—result in a highly irregular contact between the two materials. Furthermore, since the deposition of these rock units, the area has been subjected to various degrees of faulting and development of horst-and-graben-like structure, with several sets of relatively uplifted and down-dropped blocks bounded by compartment faults.

The Middle Andesite Series core samples were generally fresh to slightly weathered, from weak to strong, and brownish black, greenish gray, grayish red, and dark reddish gray. The rock was massive to porphyritic with varying amounts of coarse sand to 0.3-ft diameter clasts. Some clasts display a rind of alteration and are vitrophyric and vuggy. The vugs were partially filled with calcite, silica, and a green zeolite-like mineral. The Middle Andesite Series appears to include an autobreccia with occasional polymictic intervals that contain varicolored clasts. The clasts are in a very fine grained to aphanitic siliceous matrix. The rock was generally clast-supported with occasional intervals with a higher percentage of matrix than clasts. Fractures in the Middle Andesite Series were generally lined with calcite, silica, and chlorite with occasional pyrite.

Wall Mountain Tuff (P_{Ewm})

Wall Mountain Tuff was encountered in boreholes TT-15-20 and TT-16-20 near the East Dam and in only the deepest West Dam borehole, BH-12, at 214 ft bgs.

Highly weathered saprolite Wall Mountain Tuff (residual rock) consisted of dark reddish brown to weak red clayey sand (SC) that was loose to dense. A high-plasticity clay (CH) and low-plasticity clay (CL) were also encountered in TT-15-20 and TT-16-20. The samples had varicolored completely weathered to slightly weathered clasts up to 0.5 ft in diameter.

The Wall Mountain Tuff core was generally fresh to slightly weathered, extremely weak to weak, and dark reddish brown to medium brown and grayish brown. The rock was massive tuff in several intervals and polymictic breccia in several intervals with rounded to subangular clasts generally ranging in size from medium sand to 0.6 ft in diameter in an aphanitic matrix.

Lower Volcaniclastic Unit (P_{evc})

Rocks correlated with the Lower Volcaniclastic Unit were only encountered east of the mapped 31MBGF, in the relatively uplifted footwall, and only near the East Dam. The unit may be present west of the 31MBGF, although at depths greater than the scope of the subsurface investigation.

Weathered upper sections of the Lower Volcaniclastic Unit consist of gray to reddish gray clay and sandy clay with medium stiff to stiff consistency. Weathering degree decreases gradually with depth. Slightly weathered to fresh lithologies encountered in boreholes consisted of interbedded layers of volcanic ash and lapilli tuff, and matrix-supported breccia with iron oxidation of both the matrix and lithic, angular, clasts up to 1 inch in diameter.

The Lower Volcaniclastic Unit was found to overlie rocks correlated with the Echo Park conglomerate in areas around the East Dam, while near the Wildhorse Hills it directly overlies granitic basement rocks and related units (such as the Mafic Dikes encountered in borehole TT-23-21).

Echo Park Alluvium, Conglomerate Lithofacies (P_{eec})

Rocks correlated with the Echo Park Alluvium, Conglomerate Lithofacies directly overlay granitic basement rocks such as in borehole TT-21-21 along the East Dam alignment. Other boreholes in the area encountered the younger Lower Volcaniclastic Unit directly overlying basement rocks, possibly due to their proximity to the granitic Wildhorse Hills. The Echo Park conglomerate is mapped by Barkmann et al. (2018) to the east of the 31MBGF, where erosion on the uplifted footwall of the fault has exposed the older units of the available geologic sequence, including the granitic basement in the Hartsel Uplift and the Wildhorse Hills.

The rocks consist of clast-supported conglomerate. Clasts are of mixed lithology, subrounded to rounded and up to 0.5 ft in diameter. The matrix is primarily sandy, gray where fresh to reddish brown where oxidized, and well cemented. The rock mass has occasional fractures with secondary mineralization and areas with high content of iron oxide staining. The core samples tend to break along clast edges, since the clast size is on average greater than the diameter of the HQ-sized core.

Minturn and Maroon Formations

Clastic rocks, evaporites, and dolomite of the Minturn and Maroon formations are present in the area. They have not been observed in the reservoir footprint or in boreholes. If they are present at depth, these units are overlain by several hundred feet of volcanic deposits and likely additional sedimentary rocks.

South and west of the current footprint, dozens of closed topographic depressions trend north-northwest straddling the Agate Creek Fault. Prior work (RJH, 2020; Tetra Tech, 2021a) suggested that the depressions were the result of dissolution of the evaporite facies of the Paleozoic Minturn Formation. Reprocessing RJH seismic line 4 (Tetra Tech, 2021a) indicated a stack of east-vergent backthrusts in the hangingwall (i.e., east side) of the Agate Creek fault that appear to have transported the Minturn to within ~100 feet (~30 meters) of the surface. Moreover, multiple low-velocity pockets that may be water-filled voids were imaged near the top of the presumed Minturn evaporite facies.

Four lines of evidence suggest that the Minturn evaporites are absent beneath the current reservoir footprint, however. If they are present, they are sealed off from near-surface water by hundreds of feet of volcanic rock. First, boreholes within the proposed reservoir penetrated as much as 300 feet (90 meters) of volcanic rock, yet none encountered the Minturn. Second, on the eastern flank of the NW massif and just west of the proposed reservoir, dolomite in the overlying Upper Minturn/Lower Maroon formation sits non-conformably on granite, demonstrating that the evaporite facies is absent. Third, Barkmann et al.'s (2018) cross section A-A', which runs southwest-northeast approximately 700 meters northwest (i.e., lower in the stratigraphic section) of the proposed reservoir, shows the Upper Minturn/Lower Maroon formation buried by ~250 feet (~75 meters) of Tertiary volcanic rock and indicates that the evaporites are absent. Fourth, if the HFZ were acting as the western bounding fault of Frontrangia during Ancestral Rockies time, Barkmann et al. (2018) argue that uplift along and near the fault would have pushed the Colorado Trough shoreline westward, likely near the Agate Creek Fault, and evaporites would never have been deposited in the Paleozoic.

Mafic Dikes (Xmi)

The Mafic Dikes are near-vertical bands of aphanitic mafic rock within the host granite. The dikes are observable at ground surface in the vicinity of the East Dam alignment and were encountered in borehole TT-23-21 and near the East Dam Spillway in borehole TT-ES02-23. The mafic rocks were observed in depositional contact with the overlying volcanic ash tuff and matrix-supported breccia of the Lower Volcaniclastic Unit.

The fresh to moderately weathered core samples consist of black to greenish black aphanitic mafic rock, strongly foliated, with occasional calcite veins up to 0.5 inches in apparent thickness. The upper contact with the volcaniclastic rocks is consistent with subaerial exposure and a weathering profile from saprolite (paleosol) to fresher rock. The high degree of weathering near the contact with the volcaniclastic unit may also indicate high temperature deposition of the volcanic materials.

Granite-Quartz Monzonite Porphyry (Xgp)

The Granite-Quartz Monzonite Porphyry consists of gray to pinkish gray, coarse-grained plutonic rock. The rocks are characterized by conspicuously large potassium feldspar phenocrysts (up to 2 inches in diameter) in a crystalline matrix composed primarily of plagioclase and quartz crystals up to 0.5 inches in diameter with fine-grained magnetite and biotite. This unit intrudes the pink granite in the Main Dam area. Weathering along the contact with the granite and the discontinuities created along the highly irregular surface of the contact may have contributed to it being the preferential pathway for water flow and the formation of the canyon in the Main Dam area.

Samples in the porphyry display lower fracture density than the surrounding granite, which results in higher RQD values and more intact core lengths. The main porphyry body in the Main Dam canyon also coincides with a modest gravity high relative to the surrounding Wild Horse Hills, consistent with lower internal fracture density than in the surrounding granite. The preferential erosion of the canyon near this porphyry may therefore result from alteration of the host granite rather than weakness of the porphyry itself.

Granite and Alkali Feldspar Granite (Xg)

The granitic basement consists of pinkish gray to pink, medium crystalline granite, and is composed of potassium feldspar, quartz, plagioclase, and biotite. These rocks form the Wildhorse Hills in the surrounding areas of the Main Dam alignment and are intruded by the Granite-Quartz Monzonite Porphyry.

The granite core was generally fresh to slightly weathered, weak to medium strong, and mottled pale reddish brown, white, and light gray. The rock was crystalline with varying amounts of anhedral coarse to pegmatitic quartz, plagioclase feldspar, orthoclase feldspar, and biotite. The biotite was moderately weathered with iron oxidation. The core also contained less than one percent pyrite crystals. The granite displayed a higher degree of fracturing than the porphyry, which resulted in lower RQD values and crumbly sections of core. This observation is consistent with the hypothesis that alteration of the host granite by the porphyritic intrusion may have focused preferential incision of the main canyon.

Alteration

Several alteration zones were encountered in the Phase I, Phase II, and Phase III borings. The alteration zones are characterized by an extremely weak to weak rock strength and a pale olive, dusky yellow green, and light greenish gray color. The alteration generally appears as a rind around fractures; however, in several intervals the entire core exhibited the alteration. One such alteration zone was encountered in TT-12-20 from 232.3 feet bgs to 241 feet bgs. In TT-15-20, the matrix of the saprolitic Wall Mountain Tuff also contained alteration of 20% to 40% of the matrix.

APPENDIX C: Gravity Data Processing

Data Acquisition

Tetra Tech geophysicists have collected 3419 readings at 3027 unique locations (**Figure 6**) using a Scintrex CG-5 Autograv gravimeter (SN #121). Acquisition of each data point involved at least three readings of approximately 30 seconds duration. Each of these readings comprises six measurements per second and automated rejection of anomalous measurements. The value returned is the mean of all retained measurements (i.e., as many as 180 independent measurements for a 30s reading). Data used in post-processing and interpretation represent the median of these three readings. Sets of three readings were repeated until all three readings converged to within 0.010 mGal. At the beginning of each day's survey, approximately every three hours, and at the end of the day a base station was reoccupied for 3 to 12 readings of 60s duration; these base readings were used to account for instrumental drift and tidal effects not captured by automated corrections. Handheld GPS units recorded each station location, allowing the survey data to be merged precisely with publicly available 1-meter LiDAR DEM of the area. These precise elevation controls allowed high-fidelity Free Air, Bouguer and Terrain corrections.

To provide empirical constraints on uncertainty, measurements have been repeated on different days at ~5% of stations. These repeats agree with one another within an average of ± 0.011 mGal. This value is viewed as a proxy for the uncertainty of any single measurement. For comparison, the anomalies analyzed have amplitudes ranging from several mGal at the broadest scaled to ~0.050 mGal at the finest. Roughly 5 times the uncertainty of any single measurement, these anomalies are reliably resolved.

Data Processing

Gravity measurements include signals from subsurface density structure, but these signals are obscured by larger variations due to Earth's oblate shape, tidal effects (i.e., time-dependent variations in the gravitational pull of the moon and secondarily the sun, and associated effects), instrumental drift, the elevations of gravity stations, and topographic relief. Accounting for and removing these influences leaves only the variations due to subsurface density variations, both from the depth range and area of interest and from deeper and more distant sources; this quantity is the Complete Bouguer Anomaly (CBA). Deep and distant sources generate long-wavelength signals that also can be estimated and subtracted to isolate the signature of the materials beneath the site and from geotechnically pertinent depths, termed the "Residual Gravity Anomaly", "residual gravity", or simply "residual" (**Figure 6**).

Residual gravity anomalies are the basis of analysis and interpretation. Subsequent filtering, modeling, and analysis of the residual gravity is used to identify geologic structures, estimate depths to bedrock or thickness of specific units, or generate 3D subsurface models, among other applications.

Latitude Correction

Gravitational acceleration at the Earth's surface is approximately 9.8 m/s², or 980,000 mGal. (1 Gal = 1 cm/s²; 1 mGal = 10⁻³ Gal = 10⁻⁵ m/s²). Thus, the 0.001 mGal precision of modern gravimeters captures variations in acceleration of 10⁻⁸ m/s², or one-billionth of total gravity.

Because of Earth's equatorial bulge, however, mean sea level is farther from the Earth's center of mass at low latitudes than near the poles: Gravitational acceleration increases from 978,000 mGal at the equator to 983,200 mGal at the poles. More generally, normal gravity g_n varies with latitude ϕ as:

$$g_n = 978,031 \left(1 + 0.005278895 \sin^2(\phi) + 0.000023462 \sin^4(\phi) \right) \quad (1)$$

for g_n in units of mGal and latitude in degrees.

The value of g_n is computed for each gravity station and removed from measurements.

Drift Corrections

Tides—specifically the relative positions of the Earth, moon, and sun—create time-dependent gravity variations that are effectively uniform across a study area. Small changes in the physical properties of the gravimeter components can also cause instrumental drift. Thus, repeated measurements at one point will yield different gravity readings throughout a day and from day to day. Over periods of a few hours, tidal and instrumental drift can be closely approximated as linear variations in time; daily fluctuations of 0.500 mGal are typical. Repeating measurements at one "base" station every few hours gives empirical instrumental-plus-tidal drift as a function of time through the day, and the tidal effects can then be removed from the day's gravity measurements. Reoccupying the same base station during each field day allows multiple days' surveys to be linked into a single time-independent gravity map.

Because of the large project area, substantial drift could occur while traveling from distant gravity stations to any single base location. Therefore, a primary base location was established at the main entry gate, and secondary bases were established at five additional locations spread across the site, with the gravity value at each location tied back to the main base by at least three sets of relative measurements.

Empirical time-dependent drift curves are subtracted from the gravity measurements to yield the time-independent relative gravity values at each station.

Topographic Correction 1: The Free Air correction

Just at equatorial points are farther from the Earth's center of mass than polar locations and therefore experience lower accelerations, gravity decreases with elevation. The rate of this decrease is simply the vertical derivative of gravity evaluated at the Earth's surface (at elevation E and latitude ϕ), which works out to

$$\frac{dG}{dR} = -0.3086 - 0.0023\cos 2\phi + 0.00000002E \quad (2)$$

The latter two terms are so small that they are effectively constant across the project area.

The Free Air correction accounts for the impact of the elevation of the gravity stations, adjusting the measurements to a common reference height by adding 0.3086 mGal/m to the tide- and latitude-corrected data. This value is the Free Air Anomaly. Because the correction is linear with respect to elevation, the choice of the reference elevation is arbitrary, and "E" can simply refer to the difference between each gravity station's elevation and the reference elevation. Here, the lowest-elevation gravity station is used as the reference, so "E" is each station's height above the lowest station.

Topographic Correction 2: The Bouguer correction

The Free Air correction accounts for the impact of observation height, it does not account for the gravitational pull of the rock between the gravity stations and the reference elevation. As a result, the Free Air Anomaly is much more positive in high-elevation areas and does not provide much information on the subsurface density structure. To account for the slab of rock between the observation point and the reference height, this material is first modeled as an infinitely broad layer of density ρ from the station to the reference elevation (a thickness "E") to compute the Bouguer Correction:

$$g = -2\pi G \left(\frac{\rho E}{1000} \right) = \frac{-0.04193 \rho E}{1000} \quad (3)$$

The Bouguer Correction is negative because it removes the estimated gravitational pull from the idealized slab of rock: Higher-elevation areas have more negative Bouguer Corrections.

The density ρ can be chosen in any number of ways. To represent the average continental upper crust, many gravity surveys select 2670 kg/m³. This value is indeed roughly appropriate for the granite and granite porphyry of the Main Dam canyon and NW uplift. Alternatively, objective joint inversions for the optimal density, terrain corrections (see next section) and regional gravity field returns a values of 2552 kg/m³. As a third option, the average measured density from shallow borehole samples can be used. Recalling that "E" represents the height above the lowest station, because the average station elevation is 40 meters above the lowest the Bouguer Correction accounts for, on average, the upper 40 m of the subsurface. The average density of borehole samples from the upper 40 meters is ~2100 kg/m³. However, the high-standing crystalline bedrock areas in which the choice of density is most important are underrepresented in shallow borings, so we favor the intermediate and objectively determined value of 2552 kg/m³.

Topographic Correction 3: The Terrain Correction

The Bouguer Correction idealizes the span between each gravity station and the reference height as an infinitely broad slab of rock. This approximation is crude, and its shortcomings can generate artefacts that mask the signals of real subsurface density variations. For a gravity station next to a canyon, for example, the Bouguer Correction assumes that rock exists where there is none (in the canyon) and therefore subtracts too much from the Free Air Anomaly. For a station at the bottom of the canyon, conversely, the upward attraction of the rock above the station is ignored by the Bouguer Correction: The Bouguer Correction is again too negative. Thus, the Terrain Correction is always positive, and areas of high topographic relief will have more positive terrain corrections than flat regions. Here, a ~1°x1° USGS LiDAR 1-meter DEM is used to compute terrain corrections to distances of 5 km.

Adding the Free Air Correction, subtracting the Bouguer Correction, and finally adding the Terrain Correction to the latitude- and drift-corrected gravity gives the Complete Bouguer Anomaly (CBA). The CBA should represent the summed signals of all subsurface density variations. The signals from the depth range and

area of interest are hidden beneath the long-wavelength impacts of deeper crustal and upper mantle structure, however.

The Regional Gravity Field and Residual Gravity Anomaly

At scales of several km, the CBA is almost always dominated by deep (from a few km through upper mantle depths) and/or distant sources. These signals are not constant across the site and overprint the gravity signatures from the limited depth range and area of interest. Nevertheless, the signals change slowly across the region and can be closely approximated as linear trends (i.e., a planar surface) or other smoothly varying functions. To estimate the long-wavelength “regional” field, a surface is fit to the CBA model and then subtracted to leave a residual gravity anomaly intended to represent the gravity variations that arise from sources beneath the site:

$$CBA(x, y) \approx ax + by + c \rightarrow Residual(x, y) = CBA(x, y) - ax - by - c \quad (4)$$

The coefficients a, b, and c are derived from a least-squares fit.

Higher-order polynomials can also be used to define the regional field. A degree-2 fit takes the form:

$$CBA(x, y) = ax^2 + by^2 + cxy + dx + ey + f \quad (5)$$

Additional degrees of freedom allow the polynomial to fit progressively shorter-wavelength features. Because the breadth of the gravity signal measured at the surface scales with the depth of its source, higher-order polynomial fits isolate the signals of progressively shallower features.

The residual gravity anomaly presents the first useful information on density structure beneath the site, and it is the base for all subsequent analyses, derivative products, and models.

Isolating Signals from Pertinent Depths

Deeper density anomalies generate broader gravity signals. Therefore, removing long-wavelength patterns from the residual gravity anomaly isolates shallow sources. For simple shapes, the relationship between depth and signal width is given by analytical solutions. For instance, linear horizontal features such as dikes create signals with a width equal to 2 times the source depth. (Specifically, the “width” in this rule refers to the width of the area over which the gravity anomaly is at least half of its maximum value. Said differently, from the peak anomaly directly over the center of the dike, the gravity anomaly decays to half of its maximum amplitude over a distance equal to the depth of the dike.) For point sources or spheres—as an endmember—the width decreases to 1.54 times the source depth. Similar rules apply to the signals of other simple shapes buried in a homogenous subsurface: In most all cases, the breadth of an anomaly at the surface scales nearly linearly with source depth.

The real geometries of subsurface features complicate the relationship between gravity anomaly width and source depth. For instance, broad bodies necessarily create broad signals, regardless of their depth. A thin surficial sedimentary unit spread across a basin will create a signal across the whole basin: much broader than the deposit is deep. A suite of parallel dikes will also create a signal wider than their depth, as would a single sill-like intrusion. Importantly, however, no shape produces narrower anomalies than predicted by the analytical rules of thumb. In summary, long-wavelength signals can either be due to deep sources or to shallow, broad sources, but short-wavelength signals must be due to shallow sources.

To highlight signals from shallow density variations, the longer-wavelength (low-wavenumber) components of the gravity field are modeled and subtracted. This operation is analogous to passing the signal through a filter that removes the low-wavenumber contributions but allows the high-wavenumber contributions to pass through: termed high-pass filtering. The total signal $g(x, y)$ is partitioned into low-pass and high-pass components $LP(x, y)$ and $HP(x, y)$:

$$g(x, y) = LP(x, y) + HP(x, y); \text{ thus, } HP(x, y) = g(x, y) - LP(x, y) \quad (6)$$

High-pass/low-pass filters are typically applied in the Fourier (i.e., wavenumber) domain. These analyses require uniformly spaced, gridded models. However, a strength of relative gravity surveying is that coverage can easily be densified in areas of interest while remaining coarser in surroundings. To avoid problems that result from interpolation and to reduce computational load, we have developed a toolbox of functions for gravity analysis in the spatial domain.

Low-pass filtering can be achieved in the spatial domain by convolving the 2D gravity anomaly field $g(x, y)$ with a spatial smoothing function s

$$LP(x, y) = s * g(x, y) \quad (7)$$

Here, we s is a normalized matrix of weights that are a radially symmetric Gaussian, which shares many of the properties of the gravity signal from a point-source. As a function of radial distance d , the Gaussian $G(d)$ with a nominal length-scale of r is:

$$G(d) = \exp(-d^2/r^2) \dots s \equiv G/\text{norm}(G) \quad (8)$$

A convenient property of this function is that it approximates the gravity signal from a spherical source centered at depth r . Consequently, convolution with a 250-meter Gaussian (i.e., $r = 250$ m) nominally dampens signals from shallower than 250 meters while preserving signals from deeper than 250 meters. Thus, we are closer to achieving filtering as a function of source depth than is possible with sinusoids in the Fourier domain.

Horizontal Derivatives

The first derivative is slope or gradient. For a one-dimensional gravity profile $g(x)$, the first derivative is $dg(x)/dx$, or the difference in residual amplitude between two adjacent points divided by the distance between them. In two dimensions, the total horizontal gradient is $((dg/dx)^2 + (dg/dy)^2)^{0.5}$.

Gravity anomalies due to symmetric bodies with finite widths are flat-topped: The gradient above the center of the source body approaches 0. The locations of the peak gradient are generally rough approximations of the edges of an anomalous body (plunging features are an exception). A single elongate gravity anomaly will create two high-gradient strips, one along each edge. When viewed in two dimensions, continuous trends of relatively high gradient can be used to trace folds, faults, intrusions, and geologic contacts over long distances, even when the source is buried or the signal is locally overprinted.

Comparatively small changes in gravity that are not noticeable on a residual anomaly map can create notable signals in the gradient. While this property amplifies signals, it also amplifies noise. Second and third horizontal derivatives further accentuate small signals but can become clouded by noise. Just as the first derivative appears as two high-gradient strips along the anomaly edges, the second derivative has three bands, with the central band typically located directly above the axis of the anomaly. The central band is concave down for a gravity high and concave up for low-gravity anomalies. The third derivative creates bands along the edges of the source anomaly, but it also includes spurious additional bands parallel to the anomaly edges and well outside of the source zone. As a result, the third derivative does not identify individual features but rather creates stripes parallel to the local structural grain (e.g., parallel to fold axes). Where faulting truncates geologic structures, the third derivative strips are also truncated. Therefore, alignments of third-derivative truncations are sensitive indicators of fault traces (Levandowski et al., 2020), especially faults with lateral offsets. Truncations appear along strike-slip faults that cross-cut pre-existing structure, such as the abundant compartment faults at the site, even when no gravity signal is apparent because of the lack of vertical offset.

Total Horizontal Gradient

The horizontal gradient (**Figure 16**) outlines many of the features already discussed. The largest gradients typically surround exposures of crystalline bedrock.

- Around the NW massif, high gradients delineate the areas where low-density Tallahassee Creek laps onto the dense granites; lower gradients correspond to contacts between the granites and Volcanic Breccia and the dolomitic Minturn Formation.
- The contrast between exceptionally dense mafic intrusions in the 31MBGF footwall and the low-density sediments and Volcanic Breccia in the hangingwall is also obvious between the Main Dam canyon and Poyner Ranch Fault.
- Northeast of 31MBGF, the Poyner Ranch Fault creates a large gravity gradient between the upthrown crystalline block to the north and the volcanoclastic and sedimentary fill to the south.

Figure 16: Total horizontal gradient. Thin black lines: Faults mapped by Barkmann et al. (2018) and Tetra Tech.

Within the reservoir footprint, gradients are subdued. Subtle alternating high/low gradient bands trend NNW, which is interpreted to represent basement topography created by the Agate Creek Anticline/Syncline folds and their associated blind faults. The Poyner Ranch Fault is not associated with gravity gradients southwest of 31MBGF.

Second Derivative – Curvature

The second derivative represents curvature of the gravity field. Along the trends of gravity maxima, the gravity field is concave down, and the second derivative is negative. By contrast, positive second derivatives trace low-gravity trends.

The largest second-derivative amplitudes at the site are found on either side of 31MBGF (**Figure 17**). The most negative second-derivative strip decreases in magnitude to the northwest as it nears the Main Dam canyon, crosses the canyon near its mouth, and then becomes discontinuous near the north wall of the Main Dam canyon. This pattern is consistent with the presence of a NE-striking tear fault near the Main Dam canyon, a feature that was suggested by the separation between the full- and half-graben basins on the 31MBGF footwall. A parallel second-derivative maximum ~110 m (~350 ft) to the southwest delineates where gravity reaches a local nadir. This

observation is consistent with a listric normal fault but also could also mark the location where the fault enters basement, and the density contrast between hangingwall and footwall disappears.

High curvature on the periphery of the NW crystalline uplift and above the Agate Creek Anticline/Blind Agate Creek Thrust confirms the presence of shallow geologic structures that juxtapose units with different densities and geotechnical properties. The concave-up positive second derivative values on the eastern flank of the West Dam alignment delineate the Tallahassee Creek onlapping onto the volcanic bedrock high atop the Agate Creek Anticline, while the concave-down (red) band along the alignment reflects that structural high. Southwest of the West Dam elbow, the large hill of Tallahassee Creek manifests as an ESE-trending concave-up band (**Figure 17B**).

Figure 17: Second horizontal derivative, curvature. Negative curvature (red) coincides with gravity highs, positive curvature (blue) with lows. Black lines: Faults mapped by Barkmann et al. (2018) and Tetra Tech. (A) The greater study area. (B) Zoomed in on the proposed reservoir.

Third Derivative – Torsion

The third derivative, torsion, does not identify individual features but rather creates stripes parallel to the local structural grain.

The area around 31MBGF exemplifies this property. Along the fault, torsion bands trend northwest-southeast, parallel to the fault. These bands are bounded by the fault, however, and the crystalline footwall is dominated by northeast trends parallel to the mafic intrusions, cataclasites, and Proterozoic fault breccia. To the southeast, the Poyner Ranch Fault disrupts this pattern, juxtaposing those northeast-trending torsion bands associated with the mafic dikes against volcanoclastic and sedimentary deposits with no dominant grain and thus low torsion amplitudes.

Within the reservoir footprint, the Poyner Ranch Fault is buried by Volcanic Breccia and younger deposits, and it does not exhibit a signature in the residual anomaly or horizontal gradient. Nevertheless, it can be seen truncating numerous torsion alignments. This observation suggests that lateral motion on the fault has beheaded and/or offset antecedent structures, including the Agate Creek Anticline.

In fact, the complex mosaic of blind thrusts and compartment faults creates a collage of torsion trends, with individual faults truncating multiple sets of torsion bands of differing orientations along their length. Such alignments of torsion truncations can be used to infer the locations and trends of the subtle compartment faults that splinter the upper crust.

By contrast, the NW massif is transparent in the third-derivative map, suggesting an isotropic plutonic grain.

Figure 18: Second horizontal derivative, curvature. Negative curvature (red) coincides with gravity highs, positive curvature (blue) with lows. Black lines: Faults mapped by Barkmann et al. (2018) and Tetra Tech. (A) The greater study area. (B) Zoomed in on the proposed reservoir. Examples of changes in structural trends, evidenced by truncations of high-torsion bands, are indicated by gray arrows.

Computing Optimal Density from Elevation Dependence of Gravity Anomalies

The right arm of the West Dam was aligned along a topographic, structural, and gravity high, the Agate Creek Anticline. This ridge is interpreted as an antiform that predates Breccia deposition, such that it mostly impounded the breccia to the east. Lacustrine and fluvial deposits of the Tallahassee Creek formation overlapped this ridge from the west, infilled channels that had incised across the ridge through the breccia, and locally overtopped the divide to be deposited on the ridge and along its eastern flank (e.g., Figure 17)

A primary goal of the geophysical Investigations along the West Dam right arm is to identify and delineate pockets of the low-quality Tallahassee Creek formation (or other low-quality deposits such as Quaternary sediments or deeply weathered material) along the West Dam centerline in greater detail than is practical from borehole constraints alone.

Borehole TT31 had encountered a thick accumulation of Tallahassee Creek in a small basin beneath the right abutment, which corresponded to a pronounced short-wavelength gravity low along the otherwise high-gravity West Dam alignment (**Figure 11B**). To verify that the Tallahassee Creek formation has distinctly lower density than the Breccia, a targeted survey collected gravity data along transects up the hill of Breccia at the West Dam elbow and the taller hill of Tallahassee Creek just southwest of there (labeled “Hill of Tallahassee Ck,” on **Figure 17B**). This survey took advantage of the fact that gravity changes linearly with elevation, along a slope that is proportional to the density of the shallowest units. Specifically, the Free Air Anomaly (FAA) depends on elevation E as:

$$\text{FAA} = 0.04193\rho E; \text{dFAA/dE} = 0.04193\rho \quad (10)$$

where ρ is the density of shallow units. (The Bouguer Correction, $-0.04193\rho E$, is intended to counter this dependence so that the CBA is independent of elevation if geology is uniform.) Therefore, the slope of Free Air Anomaly vs. elevation is proportional to ρ :

$$\rho = \text{dFAA/dE} / 0.04193 \quad (11)$$

The gravity vs. elevation data indicate densities of 2540 kg/m^3 for the Breccia and 2180 kg/m^3 for the Tallahassee Creek (Figure 19).

Gravity data along the West Dam identified distinctive low-gravity anomalies along both the upstream and downstream toes, especially near the right abutment. These most pronounced lows correspond to Tallahassee Creek encountered in boreholes WD49, WD51, WD52, WD53, WD54, WD59, WD60, WD61, and TT31. These anomalies are restricted to the flanks of the alignment and do not cross the dam centerline, however. This confinement was confirmed by the absence of Tallahassee Creek in any of the Phase III centerline boreholes. Thus, there are not likely to be upstream-downstream continuous deposits of permeable Tallahassee Creek undermining the West Dam.

Figure 19: Determining shallow density from gravity vs. elevation near the West Dam knuckle. x : data from the ridge of Breccia along the alignment. o : data from the hill southwest of the elbow, which comprises Tallahassee Creek conglomerate.